

Secretagogin (SCGN) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : Secretagogin, encoded by SCGN, is expressed in a variety of organs and tissues. They have been implicated in colorectal cancers, prostate tissue, tumors of human brain including meningioma, mouse retina, human olfactory tract, central neurocytomas, small cell lung cancer, thermal and urea denaturation, autistic children, pancreatic β -cells, type 2 diabetes mellitus, cervical neuroendocrine carcinoma, hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis disorder, clear cell renal cell carcinoma, and Hepatitis C. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of SCGN, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed

^{*}ML dicoveries of SCGN synergy in Meningiomas

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at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angioma-tous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Secretagoin (SCGN)

Wagner et al. [13] cloned a novel pancreatic beta cell and neuroendocrine cell-specific Ca^{2+} -binding protein termed secretagoin. They observed that the cDNA contained an open reading frame of 828 base pairs which codes for a cytoplasmic protein with six putative EF finger hand Ca^{2+} -binding motifs. Their Northern blot analysis showed its abundant expression in the pancreas and to a lesser extent in the thyroid, cortex, and adrenal medulla. Further, it was observed that it was expressed in limited quantity in the gastrointestinal tract (stomach, colon, and small intestine). Functional analysis of

transfected cell lines expressing secretagogen revealed an influence on Ca^{2+} flux and cell proliferation.

1.3. Roles of Secretagogen

Xing et al. [14] performed comparative 2-DE of individual-matched normal and neoplastic colorectal tissue specimens to identify proteins with colorectal cancer-specific regulation. They found 15 (20) protein spots with concordantly increased (decreased) intensity in tumor tissue with an expression regulation more than fivefold; Secretagogen exhibited a marked down-regulation in **colorectal cancer** tissues. Immunohistochemistry revealed absence of secretagogen-expressing cells in most of the colorectal cancer tissue specimens and in normal mucosa, they observed that positively stained cells exhibited a neuroendocrine cell-characteristic morphology and mucosal location. Further, they found that in colorectal cancer tissues, secretagogen-expressing cells were characterized by a malignant morphology.

Previously Adolf et al. [15] reported secretagogen, a hexa-EF-hand Ca^{2+} binding protein, as a novel neuroendocrine (NE) marker in carcinoid tumors of the lung and the gastrointestinal tract. Adolf et al. [15] analyzed the expression of secretagogen in normal and malign **prostate** tissue. They found that secretagogen is cytoplasmic and nuclear expressed in NE and NE differentiated cells, and to a lesser extent in epithelial cells, in the benign prostate and prostate adenocarcinoma cells. Further, the expression of secretagogen was found to be significantly correlated to CgA and NSE in prostate adenocarcinoma and to CgA in normal epithelium.

Pipp et al. [16] investigated secretagogen expression in 245 **tumours of the human brain** and its coverings using immunohistochemistry and found focal or widespread secretagogen expression in tumour cells in 1/18 oligoastrocytomas, 1/19 oligodendrogliomas, 2/20 anaplastic oligodendrogliomas, 2/9 ependymomas, 2/11 anaplastic ependymomas, 2/10 glioblastomas, 3/11 gangliogliomas and 1/2 anaplastic gangliogliomas, 10/10 central neurocytomas, 5/10 classic medulloblastomas, 4/5 desmoplastic medulloblastomas, 3/5 large cell/anaplastic medulloblastomas, 3/5 neuroblastomas, 3/10 **meningiomas**, 2/10 haemangioblastomas, and 13/19 pituitary adenomas. Further, we observed secretagogen expression in endothelial cells in 5/10 meningiomas, 2/5 haemangiopericytomas, and 2/10 haemangioblastomas. Further, they detected no secretagogen expression in fibrillary astrocytoma, pilocytic astrocytoma, DNT, pineocytoma, pineoblastoma, subependymal giant cell astrocytoma (SEGA), atypical teratoid/rhabdoid tumour (AT/RT), or primary central nervous system lymphoma (PCNSL).

Puthussery et al. [17] localized secretagogen in the mouse, rat, and rabbit **retina** using immunofluorescence immunohistochemistry. Using subtype-specific markers and mice expressing green fluorescent protein (GFP) within specific cell classes, they found that secretagogen was expressed in Types 2/3/4/5/6 and possibly Type 8 cone bipolar cells in the mouse retina. It is supposed that secretagogen is a useful marker of cone bipolar cells for studying alterations in bipolar cell morphology during development and degeneration and further work is necessary.

Attems et al. [18] identified clusters of bipolar neurons in a previously unknown outer "shell" domain of the **human olfactory tract**, which express secretagogen. Sec-

retagogen is often coexpressed with polysialylated-neural cell adhesion molecule, β -III-tubulin, and calretinin, suggesting that these neurons represent a cell pool that might have escaped terminal differentiation into the olfactory circuitry. They hypothesized that secretagogen-containing "shell" cells may be eliminated from the olfactory axis under neurodegenerative conditions. Thus they concluded that secretagogen identified a previously undescribed cell pool modulate olfactory processing in humans.

Vasiljevic et al. [19] performed a microarray transcriptomic study to search for molecular markers that might improve diagnostic accuracy in 5 ((3 primary and 2 recurrent) **central neurocytomas** (CNs) are rare intraventricular tumors presenting a favorable prognosis after surgery. The gene expression in CNs was compared with that in four pineal parenchymal tumors, consisting of two pineocytomas (PCs) and two pineoblastomas (PBs), other periventricular tumors which may present neuronal differentiation. Of the confirmed 8 overexpressed genes via real-time RT-PCR, secretagogen (SCGN) was one of them.

Vasiljevic et al. [19] examined the expression of SCGN in clinical samples from **small cell lung cancer** (SCLC) patients and evaluated its relation with clinical prognosis. Their results showed that elevated expression of SCGN was correlated with the poorer prognosis of SCLC patients and the more significant correlation with chemosensitivity. Further, they found that knockdown of SCGN expression in H69AR and H446AR cells increased chemosensitivity via increasing cell apoptosis and cell cycle arrest of G0/G1 phase, while over-expression of SCGN reduced chemosensitivity in sensitive H69 and H446 cells. SCGN being a target of miR-494, up-regulation of miR-494 can sensitize H69AR cells to chemotherapeutic drugs. Thus their results suggested that SCGN was involved in the chemoresistance of SCLC under the regulation of miR-494.

Sanagavarapu et al. [20] studied the contribution of calcium binding and disulfide-bond formation to the stability of the secretagogen structure towards **thermal and urea denaturation**. SDS-PAGE analysis of secretagogen in reducing and non-reducing conditions identified a tendency of the protein to form dimers in a redox-dependent manner. They studied that the denaturation of apo and Ca^{2+} -loaded secretagogen by circular dichroism and fluorescence spectroscopy under conditions favoring monomer or dimer or a 1:1 monomer: dimer ratio and found significant higher stability towards urea denaturation of Ca^{2+} -loaded secretagogen compared to the apo protein. Further, they observed that reduced and Ca^{2+} -loaded secretagogen was found to refold reversibly after heating to 95°C, while both oxidized/reduced apo secretagogen was irreversibly denatured at this temperature.

Alhowikan et al. [21] determined SCGN levels in the plasma of thirty-seven (37) **autistic** children, categorized as mild-moderate and severe as indicated by their childhood autism rating scale (CARS) scores and compared with thirty (30) age and gender-matched control samples. Their results indicated that autistic children had significantly lower plasma level of SCGN than those of healthy controls. Children with severe as well as mild to moderate autism also exhibited significantly lower SCGN levels than healthy controls. They thus concluded that low SCGN plasma levels in children with ASD probably indicated that SCGN might be implicated in the pathogenesis of autism, However, asked for caution while using their data until further investigations are performed.

Secretagogin plays key roles in insulin secretion in **pancreatic β -cells**. To understand how the binding of Ca^{2+} to human SCGN (hSCGN) promoted secretion, Lee et al. [22] used mass spectrometry combined with a disulfide searching algorithm DBond. They found that the binding of Ca^{2+} to hSCGN promoted the dimerization of hSCGN via the formation of a Cys193-Cys193 disulfide bond and studies revealed that Ca^{2+} binding to the EF-hands of hSCGN induced significant structural changes that affect the solvent exposure of N-terminal region, and hence the redox sensitivity of the Cys193 residue. Further, they found that wild type hSCGN overexpression promoted insulin secretion in pancreatic β cells, while C193S-hSCGN inhibited it. Their findings suggested that insulin secretion in pancreatic cells was regulated by Ca^{2+} and ROS signaling through Ca^{2+} -induced structural changes promoting dimerization of hSCGN.

Beta cell dysfunction accompanies and drives the progression of **type 2 diabetes mellitus** (T2D), but there exist few clinical biomarkers to assess islet cell stress in humans. Secretagogin, which is enriched in pancreatic islets, demonstrates protective effects on beta cell function in animals. Hansson et al. [23] explore secretion and expression of secretagogin in relation to the T2D pathology, via study of primary human islets, beta cells and plasma samples. They found that secretagogin was abundantly and specifically expressed and secreted from human islets. Further, they observed that T2D patients had an elevated plasma level of secretagogin compared with matched healthy controls, which was confirmed in plasma of diabetic mice transplanted with human islets.

From January 2010 to December 2017, Yu et al. [24] included 44 patients with **cervical neuroendocrine carcinoma** undergoing surgery in the study group, and 55 patients with cervical non-neuroendocrine carcinoma (including 30 cases of cervical squamous cell carcinoma and 25 cases of cervical adenocarcinoma) undergoing surgery were included in the control group. Immunohistochemical staining of SCGN was performed in both groups and compared with three common neuroendocrine markers, chromogranin A, synaptophysin (Syn) and CD56 in the study group. Their results showed that the positive expression of SCGN in cervical neuroendocrine carcinoma, cervical adenocarcinoma and squamous cell carcinoma was 65.9% (29/44), 8% (2/25) and 0%, respectively. Further, the positive expression of SCGN in cervical neuroendocrine carcinoma was observed to be significantly higher than that in cervical adenocarcinoma and squamous cell carcinoma ($\chi^2=44.5$, $p<0.001$).

Electroacupuncture (EA) improves **hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis disorder** by reducing corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH) synthesis and release in the paraventricular nucleus (PVN). Secretagogin (SCGN) is closely related to stress and is involved in regulating the release of CRH. Zhang et al. [25] hypothesized that SCGN in the PVN might trigger the HPA system and be involved in EA-mediated modulation of HPA dysfunction caused by surgical trauma. Serum CRH and adrenocorticotropic hormone (ACTH) and plasma corticosterone (CORT) levels at 6 h and 24 h after hepatectomy were determined by radioimmunoassay. In summary, their findings demonstrated that EA normalized HPA axis dysfunction after surgical trauma by decreasing the transcription and synthesis of SCGN.

Infection with the deadly **rabies virus** (RABV) leads to alteration of cellular gene expression. The RABV, might be implicated in neuronal death due to an imbalance in Ca^{2+} homeostasis. Parvalbumin (PV) and Secretagogin (SCGN), two members of

the Ca²⁺-Binding Proteins (CBPs) are useful neuronal markers responsible for calcium regulation and buffering with possible protective roles against infections. Kanu et al. [26] investigated whether infection with rabies virus causes variance in expression levels of PV and SCGN using the Challenge virus standard (CVS) and Nigerian Street Rabies virus (SRV) strains. They divided 48, 4-week-old BALB/c mice strains into two test groups and challenged with RABV infection and one control group. They observed that infection with both virus strains resulted in significant increases in expression during early infection. Neurons with these CBPs might have a greater capacity to buffer calcium and be more resistant to degenerative changes caused by RABV. These implied that, when PV and SCGN expression levels were kept adequately high, the integrity of neurons might be maintained and degeneration caused by RABV infection might be prevented or stopped, hence, these were possible constituents of effective rabies therapy.

Guo et al. [27] determined the role of SCGN in the progression and prognosis of **clear cell renal cell carcinoma** (ccRCC). By evaluating SCGN expression on 252 microarrays of ccRCC tissues from different grades, they found that SCGN was absent in all the normal kidney tissues and significantly overexpressed in ccRCC tumor tissues.

Lipotoxicity could exacerbate damage to islet β -cells and play a significant role in the development of **type 2 diabetes**. In lipotoxic conditions, secretagogin abundantly expressed in islets, is found to undergo downregulation. Ouyang et al. [28] explored the role of SCGN in lipotoxicity-induced β -cell injury. Their findings showed that exposure to ox-LDL in vitro or long-term high-fat diets (HFD) in vivo, decreased SCGN expression and induced pyroptosis in β -cells. Moreover, when they restored SCGN, it partially reversed the pyroptotic cell death under ox-LDL or HFD treatments. They further observed that the downregulation of SCGN facilitated the translocation of ChREBP from the cytosol to the nucleus, thereby promoting TXNIP transcription. The upregulation of TXNIP activates the NLRP3/Caspase-1 pathway, leading to pyroptotic cell death. Their study demonstrated that lipotoxicity led to the downregulation of SCGN expression in islet β -cells, which resulted in ChREBP accumulation in the nucleus and subsequent activation of the NLRP3/Caspase-1 pyroptotic pathway. Thus, the administration of SCGN could be a potential therapeutic strategy to alleviate β -cell damage induced by lipotoxicity in type 2 diabetes.

Hepatitis C infections are the main causes of fatal clinical conditions such as cirrhosis and HCC development, and biomarkers are needed to predict the development of these complications. For this, it is imperative to determine which genes are deregulated in HCV-cells compared to healthy individuals. Yildirim et al. [29] aimed to identify the genes that are commonly up/down-regulated in HCV-infected cells using two different databases. Their results showed that in HCV-infected cells, the CXCL10 expression increased in both databases, while the SCGN and H2BC5 (HIST1H2BD) expression decreased. Predicted overlapping miRNAs targeted by common differentially expressed genes (DEGs) found 22 where SCGN was the estimated target.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [30] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [31] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [31].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on

gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [32]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formating the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [33], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [30] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tunned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [30]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [34], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")` • use `source("manuscript-2-2.R")` • use `source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R")`.

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings

provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. SCGN related synergies

Note - SCGN was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 2^{nd} order combinations of SCGN were recorded.

3.1.1. SCGN - individual genes

The following genes in combination with SCGN showed high rankings - mitochondrial calcium uniporter dominant negative subunit beta (MCUB), glycoprotein M6B (GPM6B), testis associated actin remodelling kinase 2 (TESK2), calmodulin regulated spectrin associated protein family member 3 (CAMSAP3), immunoglobulin superfamily member 9 (IGSF9), parathyroid hormone like hormone (PTH1LH), PITPNM family member 3 (PITPNM3), ezrin (EZR), tolloid like 2 (TLL2), apolipoprotein L4 (APOL4), neurotensin receptor 1 (NTSR1), eukaryotic translation elongation factor 1 alpha 2 (EEF1A2), ring finger protein 24 (RNF24), mesothelin (MSLN), neurocalcin delta (NCALD), tight junction protein 3 (TJP3), glutamate ionotropic receptor kainate type subunit 5 (GRIK5), RUN domain containing 3B (RUNDC3B), cordon-bleu WH2 repeat protein (COBL), Rap guanine nucleotide exchange factor like 1 (RAPGEFL1), protein arginine methyltransferase 8 (PRMT8), RNA binding motif protein 24 (RBM24), leucine rich repeat containing 31 (LRRC31), peroxisomal biogenesis factor 5 like (PEX5L), acyl-CoA dehydrogenase long chain (ACADL), interleukin 1 receptor like 1 (IL1RL1), glutaminyl-peptide cyclotransferase (QPCT), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily C member 4 (KCNC4), SSX family member 2 interacting protein (SSX2IP), interferon regulatory factor 6 (IRF6), phospholipid phosphatase related 4 (PLPPR4), solute carrier family 16 member 7 (SLC16A7), periplakin (PPL), cyclin and CBS domain divalent metal cation transport mediator 1 (CNNM1), hippocalcin (HPCA), nuclear factor, erythroid 2 (NFE2), ATP binding cassette subfamily C member 4 (PEL blood group) (ABCC4), proline rich and Gla domain 3 (PRRG3), brain expressed X-linked 2 (BEX2), serine/threonine kinase 26 (STK26), BICD family like cargo adaptor 1 (BICDL1), ETS homologous factor (EHF), HECT, C2 and WW domain containing E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 2 (HECW2), cyclin dependent kinase like 2 (CDKL2), PILR alpha associated neural protein (PIANP), collagen type II alpha 1 chain (COL2A1), MAM domain containing glycosylphosphatidylinositol anchor 2 (MDGA2), maelstrom spermatogenic transposon silencer (MAEL), cellular retinoic acid binding protein 2 (CRABP2), HHIP like 2 (HHIPL2), thrombospondin type 1 domain containing 7B (THSD7B), coiled-coil domain containing 150 (CCDC150), atypical chemokine receptor 3 (ACKR3), gamma-aminobutyric acid type A receptor subunit beta2 (GABRB2), lipocalin 2 (LCN2), coiled-coil do-

main containing 81 (CCDC81), cadherin 8 (CDH8), family with sequence similarity 124 member A (FAM124A), coiled-coil domain containing 3 (CCDC3), chondrolectin (CHODL), solute carrier family 26 member 2 (SLC26A2), glutamate receptor interacting protein 1 (GRIP1), F-box protein 32 (FBXO32), grainyhead like transcription factor 3 (GRHL3), chloride intracellular channel 6 (CLIC6), spondin 2 (SPON2), C3 and PZP like alpha-2-macroglobulin domain containing 8 (CPAMD8), cytochrome c oxidase subunit 6B2 (COX6B2), AKNA domain containing 1 (AKNAD1), sphingosine-1-phosphate phosphatase 2 (SGPP2), carboxypeptidase A3 (CPA3), neuropeptide Y receptor Y1 (NPY1R), hyperpolarization activated cyclic nucleotide gated potassium channel 1 (HCN1), STEAP family member 1 (STEAP1), defensin beta 1 (DEFB1), transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V member 6 (TRPV6), aquaporin 3 (Gill blood group) (AQP3), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein like (PHYHIPL), sodium voltage-gated channel beta subunit 3 (SCN3B), glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase 1 (GPD1), dynein axonemal assembly factor 3 (DNAAF3), phospholipase A and acyltransferase 5 (PLAAT5 / HRASLS5), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein (PHYHIP), neuronal vesicle trafficking associated 1 (NSG1), mucin 3A, cell surface associated (MUC3A), potassium two pore domain channel subfamily K member 3 (KCNK3), lysophosphatidic acid receptor 3 (LPAR3), membrane bound glycerophospholipid O-acyltransferase 1 (MBOAT1), tryptase alpha/beta 1 (TPSAB1), syntrophin gamma 2 (SNTG2), carboxylesterase 4A (CES4A), ciliary microtubule associated protein 3 (PIFO / CIMAP3), leucine rich repeat and Ig domain containing 2 (LINGO2), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 2A1 (SLCO2A1), myosin ID (MYO1D), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 2 (KCNA2), G protein-coupled receptor 4 (GPR4), transmembrane protein 30B (TMEM30B), synemin (SYNM), receptor interacting serine/threonine kinase 4 (RIPK4), family with sequence similarity 162 member B (FAM162B), aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 family member A3 (ALDH1A3), brain expressed X-linked 5 (BEX5), oxysterol binding protein 2 (OSBP2), short chain dehydrogenase/reductase family 42E, member 1 (SDR42E1), limbic system associated membrane protein (LSAMP), NF2, moesin-ezrin-radixin like (MERLIN) tumor suppressor (NF2), metallophosphoesterase domain containing 1 (MPPED1), FAT atypical cadherin 4 (FAT4), tryptase beta 2 (TPSB2), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 1 (ENPP1), family with sequence similarity 120A2, pseudogene (C9orf129 / FAM120A2P) and SEC14 like lipid binding 6 (SEC14L6).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of SCGN with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t SCGN with SCGN - > MCUB / GPM6B / TESK2 / CAMSAP3 / IGSF9 / PTHLH / PITPNM3 / EZR / TLL2 / APOL4 / NTSR1 / EEF1A2 / RNF24 / MSLN / NCALD / TJP3 / GRIK5 / RUNDC3B / COBL / RAPGEFL1 / PRMT8 / RBM24 / LRRC31 / PEX5L / ACADL / IL1RL1 / QPCT / KCNC4 / SSX2IP / IRF6 / PLPPR4 / SLC16A7 / PPL / CNNM1 / HPCA / NFE2 / ABCC4 / PRRG3 / BEX2 / STK26 / BICDL1 / EHF / HECW2 / CDKL2 / PIANP /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS SCGN									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T SCGN									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
MCUB - SCGN	172	160	151	84	GPM6B - SCGN	274	104	148	237
TESK2 - SCGN	259	305	89	198	CAMSAP3 - SCGN	213	148	94	242
IGSF9 - SCGN	218	130	223	292	PTHLH - SCGN	271	154	283	223
PITPNM3 - SCGN	229	38	204	297	EZR - SCGN	243	77	180	253
TLL2 - SCGN	144	117	273	205	APOL4 - SCGN	81	293	146	174
NTSR1 - SCGN	142	175	263	13	EEF1A2 - SCGN	188	253	289	245
RNF24 - SCGN	31	227	246	155	MSLN - SCGN	279	105	299	164
NCALD - SCGN	198	27	144	293	TJP3 - SCGN	183	90	242	147
GRIK5 - SCGN	277	132	268	303	RUNDC3B - SCGN	280	47	227	263
COBL - SCGN	246	13	253	203	RAPGEFL1 - SCGN	240	183	64	178
PRMT8 - SCGN	250	146	257	141	RBM24 - SCGN	129	193	249	160
LRRC31 - SCGN	224	36	208	208	PEX5L - SCGN	227	145	185	111
ACADL - SCGN	41	264	230	200	IL1RL1 - SCGN	294	215	295	86
QPCT - SCGN	239	151	241	161	KCNC4 - SCGN	54	182	192	194
SSX2IP - SCGN	200	235	98	209	IRF6 - SCGN	232	304	258	304
PLPPR4 - SCGN	263	250	303	94	SLC16A7 - SCGN	196	207	171	247
PPL - SCGN	152	52	159	273	CNNM1 - SCGN	161	102	189	301
HPCA - SCGN	159	276	202	62	NFE2 - SCGN	190	133	150	264
ABCC4 - SCGN	140	170	181	272	PRRG3 - SCGN	287	167	264	144
BEX2 - SCGN	248	271	279	101	STK26 - SCGN	79	277	160	280
BICDL1 - SCGN	78	214	170	232	EHF - SCGN	95	285	168	286
HECW2 - SCGN	155	85	217	235	CDKL2 - SCGN	216	83	145	267
PIANP - SCGN	132	282	291	216	COL2A1 - SCGN	153	248	198	281
MDGA2 - SCGN	170	186	243	250	MAEL - SCGN	235	142	305	6
CRABP2 - SCGN	162	187	134	204	HHIPL2 - SCGN	306	51	203	156
THSD7B - SCGN	163	281	166	261	CCDC150 - SCGN	82	286	238	199
ACKR3 - SCGN	273	68	154	295	GABRB2 - SCGN	233	121	224	243
LCN2 - SCGN	203	69	251	265	CCDC81 - SCGN	130	178	164	213

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between SCGN VS Individual members.

COL2A1 / MDGA2 / MAEL / CRABP2 / HHIPL2 / THSD7B / CCDC150 / ACKR3 / GABRB2 / LCN2 / CCDC81 / CDH8 / FAM124A / CCDC3 / CHODL / SLC26A2 / GRIP1 / FBXO32 / GRHL3 / CLIC6 / SPON2 / CPAMD8 / COX6B2 / AKNAD1 / SGPP2 / CPA3 / NPY1R / HCN1 / STEAP1 / DEFB1 / TRPV6 / AQP3 / PHYHIPL / SCN3B / GPD1 / DNAAF3 / PLAAT5 / PHYHIP / NSG1 / MUC3A / KCNK3 / LPAR3 / MBOAT1 / TPSAB1 / SNTG2 / CES4A / PIFO / LINGO2 / SLCO2A1 / MYO1D / KCNA2 / GPR4 / TMEM30B / SYNM / RIPK4 / FAM162B / ALDH1A3 / BEX5 / OSBP2 / SDR42E1 / LSAMP / NF2 / MPPED1 / FAT4 / TPSB2 / ENPP1 / C9orf129 / SEC14L6.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic SCGN 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of SCGN-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS SCGN									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T SCGN									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CDH8 - SCGN	221	230	195	288	FAM124A - SCGN	256	81	207	298
CCDC3 - SCGN	293	150	214	127	CHODL - SCGN	241	191	267	236
SLC26A2 - SCGN	186	244	92	284	GRIP1 - SCGN	53	224	167	152
FBXO32 - SCGN	244	39	270	222	GRHL3 - SCGN	192	213	77	294
CLIC6 - SCGN	143	258	213	278	SPON2 - SCGN	237	196	128	182
CPAMD8 - SCGN	212	3	215	306	COX6B2 - SCGN	231	12	284	167
AKNAD1 - SCGN	182	55	212	277	SGPP2 - SCGN	205	33	274	225
CPA3 - SCGN	290	136	245	180	NPY1R - SCGN	278	181	306	224
HCN1 - SCGN	269	219	300	59	STEAP1 - SCGN	177	288	205	46
DEFB1 - SCGN	291	197	287	63	TRPV6 - SCGN	169	211	158	251
AQP3 - SCGN	158	166	265	20	PHYHIP1 - SCGN	249	190	76	238
SCN3B - SCGN	180	192	29	226	GPD1 - SCGN	167	262	244	118
DNAAF3 - SCGN	150	172	124	276	HRASLS5 - SCGN	296	225	220	233
PHYHIP - SCGN	226	265	210	97	NSG1 - SCGN	160	297	169	269
MUC3A - SCGN	298	234	301	2	KCNK3 - SCGN	225	194	277	179
LPAR3 - SCGN	174	129	228	151	MBOAT1 - SCGN	168	212	183	165
TPSAB1 - SCGN	282	143	175	176	SNTG2 - SCGN	215	300	276	184
CES4A - SCGN	204	247	179	192	PIFO - SCGN	90	274	190	183
LINGO2 - SCGN	207	49	172	300	SLCO2A1 - SCGN	268	123	209	202
MYO1D - SCGN	275	80	234	217	KCNA2 - SCGN	154	302	248	188
GPR4 - SCGN	211	273	155	71	TMEM30B - SCGN	104	245	222	218
SYNM - SCGN	157	206	211	260	RIPK4 - SCGN	289	280	161	195
FAM162B - SCGN	236	106	221	254	ALDH1A3 - SCGN	242	41	233	189
BEX5 - SCGN	197	78	254	214	OSBP2 - SCGN	223	228	139	285
SDR42E1 - SCGN	301	4	200	207	LSAMP - SCGN	199	17	247	157
NF2 - SCGN	185	303	236	187	MPPED1 - SCGN	258	57	280	185
FAT4 - SCGN	255	42	157	279	TPSB2 - SCGN	209	101	177	149
ENPP1 - SCGN	206	307	156	227	C9orf129 - SCGN	52	231	218	283
SEC14L6 - SCGN	261	240	149	246					

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between SCGN VS Individual members.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t SCGN

MCUB / GPM6B / TESK2 / CAMSAP3 / IGSF9...
PTHLH / PITPNM3 / EZR / TLL2 / APOL4 ...
NTSR1 / EEF1A2 / RNF24 / MSLN / NCALD ...
TJP3 / GRIK5 / RUNDC3B / COBL / RAPGEFL1 ...
PRMT8 / RBM24 / LRRC31 / PEX5L / ACADL ...
IL1RL1 / QPCT / KCNC4 / SSX2IP / IRF6 ...
PLPPR4 / SLC16A7 / PPL / CNNM1 / HPCA ...
NFE2 / ABCC4 / PRRG3 / BEX2 / STK26 ...
BICDL1 / EHF / HECW2 / CDKL2 / PIANP ...
COL2A1 / MDGA2 / MAEL / CRABP2 / HHIPL2 ...
THSD7B / CCDC150 / ACKR3 / GABRB2 / LCN2 ...
CCDC81 / CDH8 / FAM124A / CCDC3 / CHODL ...
SLC26A2 / GRIP1 / FBXO32 / GRHL3 / CLIC6 ...
SPON2 / CPAMD8 / COX6B2 / AKNAD1 / SGPP2 ...
CPA3 / NPY1R / HCN1 / STEAP1 / DEFB1 / TRPV6 ...
AQP3 / PHYHIPL / SCN3B / GPD1 / DNAAF3 ...
PLAAT5 / PHYHIP / NSG1 / MUC3A / KCNK3 ...
LPAR3 / MBOAT1 / TPSAB1 / SNTG2 / CES4A ...
PIFO / LINGO2 / SLCO2A1 / MYO1D / KCNA2 ...
GPR4 / TMEM30B / SYNM / RIPK4 / FAM162B ...
ALDH1A3 / BEX5 / OSBP2 / SDR42E1 / LSAMP ...
NF2 / MPPED1 / FAT4 / TPSB2 / ENPP1 ...
C9orf129 / SEC14L6 SCGN

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between SCGN and Individual members.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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